

POST-PANDEMIC CHALLENGES CONCERNING FEMININE VS MASCULINE LEADERSHIP

Author(s)*: Cristina CÎRTIȚĂ-BUZOIANU¹, Valentin ZICHIL², Cătălin DROB³,
Brîndușa-Mariana AMĂLĂNCEI⁴

Position: Assoc. Prof., PhD¹, Prof., PhD², Assoc. Prof., PhD³, Assoc. Prof., PhD⁴

University: "Vasile Alecsandri" University of Bacau

Address: Bacau, Marasesti Street, No. 157, Romania

Email: buzoianu.cristina@ub.ro 1, valentinz@ub.ro 2, catad@ub.ro 3, amalancei.brindusa@ub.ro4

Webpage: <http://www.ub.ro/>

Abstract

Purpose – The main contribution of the study is highlighting the differences between the female and male leadership style. The study will try to define from the investigated leaders a profile of a male/female leader, the most important values put into practice and the pandemic and post-pandemic challenges they had to face.

Methodology/approach - The study aims to explore the profile of a leader by conducting semi-structured interviews with businesswomen and businessmen in order to establish the main personal and professional characteristics which contribute to a successful career.

Findings – The results of the study show which of the leadership styles, male or female, makes the difference in successful companies and in which areas they operate. The data obtained will also highlight the changes that the leaders made after the pandemic in order to adapt to the new working conditions.

Research limitations/implications – While the study has highlighted that there is a different way of practising management which values other skills and abilities, the results show that successful women are able to use the feminine values in the style of management in certain areas of activity.

Practical implications – The valorisation of personal skills in a pandemic context could balance the two types of leadership.

Originality/value – The main contribution of the study is highlighting the specific elements regarding post-pandemic challenges concerning feminine vs masculine male vs. female leadership.

Key words: male vs. female leadership, successful leadership, post-pandemic, leadership style.

Introduction

The literature on leadership is full of theories, definitions and classifications. These have undergone constant changes and developments throughout the years in line with both historical and economic events. The 19th century was dominated by the "Great Man" theory, according to which leaders are born and not made. One of the most famous supporters of this theory, Thomas Carlyle, believed the history of mankind is nothing more than a collection of great man biographies.

In the 1930s and 1940s, another theory of leadership, derived from the "Great Man" theory and known as the Trait theory, emerged. Unlike the "Great Man" theory, the Trait theory starts from the assumption that leaders can be born or made. This theory postulates that a leader's efficacy is determined by the traits or character a leader possesses (Verawati, D.M. and B. Hartono, 2020). One of the most representative exponents of this theory, Ralph Stogdill, tried to identify the most important traits defining an authentic leader. In his opinion, these traits include intelligence, insight, responsibility, initiative, persistence, self-confidence and social skills.

Between the 1940s and 1950s, the Trait Theory evolved into the Behavioural Theory. This new approach considers that a leader's success is based more on his/her behaviour and less on his/her innate traits. The paradigm of this theory can be summarised as follows: leaders are made, not born. Thus, a leader can be effective if he or she is willing to learn and implement appropriate behaviours.

After 1960, a new theory of leadership made its presence felt, namely the Contingency Theory or Situational Leadership. The essence of this theory can be concentrated in the following sentence, assigned to Paul Hersey and Kenneth H. Blanchard: Effective leaders need to be flexible and must adapt themselves according to the situation. There is no best leadership style, but the better the leadership style is, the better it will adapt to the environment (Hersey, P. and K.H. Blanchard, 1988).

After the 1990s, other leadership theories developed, the most famous being the Transactional, Transformational, Collaborative and Servant theories. The transactional theory is based on the idea that the act of leadership is a transaction, a social exchange between a leader and followers (a cost-benefit exchange), based on a system of rewards and punishments applied by the leader to the followers in order to achieve the best performance by the followers. A diametrically opposed approach is taken by the Transformational Theory, which considers that a true leader must be able to inspire, encourage and motivate subordinates so that together they can achieve the best results for the company. The transformational leadership has four components: idealised influence, inspirational motivation to enhance confidence, intellectual stimulation, and individualised consideration (Bass, B.M., 1990).

The key element of the Collaborative Theory derives from the name of the theory, namely collaboration. Collaborative leadership involves the development of mutually beneficial relationships between leaders and followers, based on trust and mutual respect, in which organisational interests prevail over individual interests. This collaboration requires decentralisation of power and the involvement of followers in decision-making so that organisational objectives are properly achieved.

The Servant Theory is a more recent approach to leadership in which the leader focuses on the subordinates' needs, putting their professional development first. The servant leader leads with love (in a social and moral sense), acts with humility, is altruistic, visionary, trusting and serving (Dennis, R.S. and Bocarnea, M., 2005).

The on-going development of leadership theories has also led to changes in the definition of leadership, the modern one differing from the traditional one. While the original definition of leadership focused more on the characteristics of a leader, today leadership is often defined as a process by which the leader influences a group of individuals through various tools in order to reach a common goal.

Leadership and gender differences

Most research and management literature attempts to establish, without discussing gender differences, typologies of leadership styles and models which are most relevant to organisational circumstances and external cultural contexts. However, as a result of the increase in the number of women in leadership positions, some possible differences between men and women (Pew Research Center, 2008) have been identified in terms of the advantages and disadvantages of the management styles adopted, but no consensus has been reached on this point. The under-representation of women in managerial positions (Cornet, A. and Cadalen, S., 2009), highlighted in the conclusions of a Eurostat statistics of March 2020 at the level of companies in the European Union, has also been explained. The only exception is Latvia, with 53% of women in managerial positions, Romania being in the mid-ranking, below the EU average of 37% (Faier, S., 2021).

The fact that relatively few women occupy top management positions is explained not by their cognitive inferiority, but by a much greater societal recognition of traits associated with masculinity. Businesswomen have been wrongly labelled a 'masculinised version of women', although there is no research to prove that women's success in male-dominated management positions is due to changes in personality or emotional life. In fact, it is not a question of an androgynisation of femininity, but of a social perception based on the idea of the hegemony of masculinity. However, it is considered that successful women in top management have a planning ability, strategic thinking, making responsible decisions that lead to company profit (Stănculescu, E., 2009).

Some authors (Loden, M., 1985) support the existence of masculine styles of management, characterised by competition, hierarchical authority and emphasis on control, and feminine styles of management, focused more on consensus, which can facilitate corporate decision-making and encourage creativity. The female leadership style would be interactive, relationship-oriented, transformational, focused on emotions, participation, sharing power and information, motivating followers, tasks and results, bonding people and things (Cornet, A. and Bonnivert, S., 2008). However, in organisational studies, beyond a number of stereotypes that women are more relationship-oriented

and men more task-oriented, there is no evidence of differences between male and female leadership styles. These differences are found in laboratory experiments and assessment studies on men and women who do not necessarily hold leadership positions. The three types of studies show only a more autocratic leadership style for men and a more democratic one for women (Eagly, A.H. and Johnson, B.T., 1990).

In an article on women's management and leadership, Frédérique Pigeyre and Philippe Vernazobres (2013) discuss three works they consider relevant and significant on this topic: *Le management au féminin* (Renaud-Boulart, 2005), *Le leadership au masculin et au féminin* (Cherret de la Boissière, 2009), *Le leadership au féminin* (Fourès, 2010) / *Female management* (Renaud-Boulart, 2005), *Male and female leadership* (Cherret de la Boissière, 2009), *Female leadership* (Fourès, 2010) which convey stereotypes about the differences between men and women, asserting the existence of specifically female competences. Thus, for M. Renaud-Boulart, female leaders act energetically and intensely, are task- and result-oriented, organise their work, emphasise their emotions, show enthusiasm and commitment to their work, whereas male leaders have more strategic skills, are more calculated, control their emotions and deal objectively with problems. According to A. Cherret de La Boissière, female leaders focus on tasks, are pragmatic, promote their results less, respect rules, are committed, responsible, aim for collective success, anticipate and manage risks, use complicity to make themselves liked and/or recognised, know how to listen, are empathetic, diplomatic, encourage dialogue and questions, express their emotions; male leaders, for their part, make their actions known, have a strategic vision and a logical and analytical approach, are self-confident, performance-oriented, take risks and responsibilities, manage energetically, decide and arbitrate without conciliation and without emotional involvement, naturally use authority and charisma. Finally, E. Fourès considers that female leaders show courage, the ability to achieve results, efficiency, intuition, motivation, determination, a humanistic approach, care about work-life balance, adopt an affectionate and proxemically oriented leadership style, lead teams focused on results, while men focus on defending territory, networking, influencing. Beyond these considerations, which perpetuate stereotypes about the differences between men and women, Frédérique Pigeyre and Philippe Vernazobres (2013) conclude that the promotion of female management seems an ambivalent approach, which would lead both to the development of diversity within the organisation and to the practice of different managerial styles.

According to a relatively recent study (Champoux-Paillé, L., 2021), a new, more feminine form of leadership has emerged during the COVID-19 pandemic in business. This conclusion is in line with the results of another study conducted, also in 2021, by McKinsey & Company et LeanIn.Org in 423 American and Canadian companies. Thus, women were able to exercise stronger leadership than men when employees' well-being became more important at the organisational level (through actions to support team members, helping colleagues manage work from home, or caring for their colleagues' mental health). The study also found that women are almost twice as supportive as their male colleagues of other women or employees from minority groups, through mentoring or sponsorship, and in this way contribute to a better working climate and to retaining or increasing the number of employees, in the context of a general labour crisis.

Certainly, the existence or not of different management styles according to gender, far from being based on indisputable scientific work, cannot be analysed outside the cultural and national context, which influences gender stereotypes, or outside the dominant organisational culture.

Data analysis

The research aims to a better exploiting of professional knowledge, managerial communication skills and interaction between leaders and subordinates. At the same time, our research seeks to identify how businesswomen can succeed and underline their managerial abilities beyond the stereotypes.

The qualitative research was designed to investigate the differences in managerial style between men and women, the challenges generated by the emergence of the pandemic and how leadership has been influenced, as well as the factors contributing to stereotyping in women's undertaking of leadership roles in specific business areas. Accordingly, we conducted 16 semi-structured interviews in Bacau, Romania (7 men and 9 women in leadership positions and aged between 32 and 70). The areas in which the investigated subjects work are: education, economics, public administration, informatics, entrepreneurship, engineering, automotive industry and sport.

As a first step, we were interested in surveying which values prevail in the organisation and whether we can speak of a well-defined organisational culture. The majority of the subjects consider that there is a well-defined organisational culture, based on values such as: integrity, transparency in decision-making, honesty, responsibility, adaptability, equality, loyalty, efficiency, performance, sense of duty, communication, tolerance, respect. This wide range of listed values shows that top management tries to implement them in the way they relate to employees or in the way the organisation is perceived by both external and internal public.

Questioned whether there is a difference between management and leadership, 15 respondents consider that the concepts are different and only 1 respondent thinks that the two can overlap conceptually, although few of them were able to provide relevant explanations as to the specific difference between the two terms. Management is the activity of guiding, coordinating, directing a group of people, an organisation, in order to achieve predetermined objectives. Leadership is the ability to create vision, motivation and momentum in a group of people, often through the use of psycho-behavioural tools (Male, 46 years old, public administration field). "Management is about leading an entity effectively. Leadership is about inspiring people, structures and facilitating their progress in an innovative way" (Female, 57, IT field).

In response to the question of what main professional/personal skills a leader should possess, the respondents mentioned: creativity, honesty, altruism, resilience, professional knowledge, adaptability, visionary, creator of change contexts, initiative, intuition, responsibility, altruism, intelligence, good communicator. We can see that personal skills predominate and that they are also extended to the organisational level, integrated into the elements belonging to the organisational culture. The managerial style adopted is closely related to personal skills. 11 out of 16 subjects state that they follow the participative style, 2 respondents - the authoritarian style, 1 respondent - the conciliatory style, 1 subject - the mixed style and 1 subject answered that it depends on the context.

The majority of subjects also consider that the style is influenced by personality, but is also adapted to the area in which they work (10 of those surveyed), that it is strictly personality-related (4 respondents), while a small segment considers that it must be adapted according to the professional area (2 subjects). The data highlight that managers put their personal touch on the way they undertake the management of an organisation, but they also take into account the specifics of the field in order to make their work more efficient, which shows adaptability and tolerance. The leadership literature often inoculates the idea that a leader is an extension of the organisation or that a leader's personality can radically change the organisational culture.

Regarding the managerial profile of a woman compared to the managerial profile of a man, the responses collected showed that there are significant differences for 15 of the subjects, while one respondent considers that there are no differences: "A woman is professionally well prepared, but less managerial, full of confidence in her own strengths (and not only), authoritarian (to impose herself on men), charming (in some cases), slippery, more empathetic than men. The male manager is ambitious, authoritarian with opponents and more democratic with others, a good professional, persevering (but also in mistakes), manipulative" (Female, 54 years old, education field). "A female manager is a good organiser, planning-oriented, monitoring-oriented, generally able to take all those measures necessary for the smooth running of things. The male manager, by nature, controls, supervises, hires, fires, and generally manages activities involving the exercise of authority, the aim being the smooth running of these activities" (Male, 32, engineering field).

To the question "Do you think there are significant differences between female and male leaders?", 14 people answered that there are differences based mainly on communication skills, intuition, negotiation/mediation skills, authority, moral profile, image, emotional intelligence, diplomacy, patience. However, respondents recognize that some and others can be exceptional leaders, while 2 subjects consider that there are no gender differences. The image of a leader is related to how others interpret his decisions and actions. The imagological construction of a nation is based on categories, stereotypes, prejudices and social labelling, positive as well as negative, which once created and spread become illustrative for the way they are perceived (Pew Research Center, 2008). Although, all of these imagological elements are often difficult to be defined and differentiated, they contribute to creating the social image and the specific defining features of a nation and the way they think and act (Daba-Buzoianu, Cîrțiță-Buzoianu, 2014: 677-678).

We asked our subjects if they could list some gender stereotypes about leadership. The answers summarise some suggestive examples: "Men are born leaders, Engineering is not for women, Women and men have different skills" (Female, 54 years old, field of education), "Women are not interested in success as much as men" (Male, 32 years old, field of engineering), "Women have to take more of the traditional role of mother and wife, Men have to bring in money and social status" (Female, 54 years old, field of economics). From the collected answers we can see that these stereotypes are known, from professional practice and that they apply both ways. Corroborated with the answers to the previous questions, i.e. the three questions that focused on the managerial profile of a woman/man and the differences between male and female leaders, we can notice that in professional practice there are still reminiscences of the existence of these stereotypes, but not in a radical way, there is also a tendency to refine and reinterpret, through the power of example, certain imagological barriers. This also emerged from the answers given to the question "whether there are certain areas or situations in which women leaders are more suitable than men". 7 out of 16 respondents believe that leadership is not related to gender but to professional training. 9 people believe that there are areas where women are more suitable, such as: public relations, human resources, education, health, commerce, advertising and economics. The next two questions asked how leaders coped organisationally with the limitations imposed by the pandemic and whether there were changes in leadership after the pandemic. "There was a need to adapt quickly in terms of organisation, technology and relationships. Decisions were reconsidered and there was a constant evaluation of them" (Female, 57 years old, education domain) "Management was done by rethinking the work schedule and making employees responsible for their health and the health of those around them. Unfortunately it also required downsizing and reducing the working hours of non-essential staff, retaining critical manpower in key positions in the organisation" (Male, 32, engineering domain). The majority of respondents felt that there had been no major changes in the way they were managed after the pandemic, but that they were more attentive to the needs of their employees' personal lives and health.

The last question surveyed "what was the most difficult situation you faced in your job and how did you manage to overcome it?" "One difficult situation was when some of my colleagues in the subordinate services got sick with COVID-19 and there were very short deadlines to finish some activities, but through effective communication I was able to get support from colleagues in other services, they joined in by putting in much more effort, working overtime to finish all activities on time" (Male, 45 years old, public administration). Among the difficulties listed were: lack of involvement of employees, delegation of tasks, recognition of the authority of younger leaders, radical decisions they took, resolving internal conflicts at organisational level or handling situations with ethical implications. This range of issues is a reflection of the way in which, on the one hand, leaders build their identity and strengthen their image at organisational level and, on the other, how they relate to their subordinates in various crisis situations.

Discussion and conclusions

The interviews indicate that the leaders of a business are aware of the differences in style, the main advantages and disadvantages compared to the men are in the collaboration with the employers and in the stereotypes that they had to face.

Although there are not very clear differences between the two leadership styles (male vs. female), based on the interviews it emerged that the respondents recognise that there are stereotypes related to women leaders, different ways of coordinating work within the organisation or certain areas where they can perform. The challenges brought by the pandemic have led leaders to take on new roles or adapt quickly to the new working conditions. Personal skills have been important in managing this crisis situation, and the post-pandemic management is increasingly focusing on employees' personal needs and health issues to ensure an optimal workplace climate.

References

Bass, B.M.

1990

"From Transactional to Transformational Leadership: Learning to Share the Vision", *Organizational Dynamics*, 18: 19–32.

Cornet, A., Bonnivert, S.

2008

"Leadership et genre", in Cornet, A., Laufer, J, Belghiti-Mahut, S., (Coord.), *GRH et genre. Les défis de l'égalité hommes-femmes*, Paris, Vuibert, 125-138.

Champoux-Paillé, L.

2021

"Le leadership féminin, une nouvelle vague là pour de bon?"; <https://lactualite.com/lactualite-affaires/le-leadership-au-feminin-une-nouvelle-vague-la-pour-de-bon/>.

Cornet, A., Cadalen, S.

2009

"Leadership et genre: regard croisé de la gestion et de la psychanalyse"; https://www.researchgate.net/publication/277203862_Leadership_et_genre_regard_croise_de_la_gestion_et_de_la_psychanalyse.

Daba-Buzoianu, C., Cîrțiță-Buzoianu, C.

2014

"Romanians' ethno-image in the national press: a comparative study of 2011 and 2012" in *Procedia – Social and Behavioral Sciences*, Volume 143, 677–681.

Dennis, R.S. and M. Bocarnea.

2005

"Development of the servant leadership assessment instrument" in *Leadership & Organization Development Journal*, Vol. 26, 8: 600–615.

Eagly, A.H., Johnson, B.T.

1990

"Gender and Leadership Style: A Meta-Analysis", *CHIP Documents*. 11; https://opencommons.uconn.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=1010&context=chip_docs.

Faier, S.

2021

"Egalitatea de gen în funcții de conducere: clișee și stereotipuri"; / "Gender equality in leadership: clichés and stereotypes"; <https://revistacariere.ro/leadership/contribuitori/egalitatea-de-gen-in-functii-de-conducere-clisee-si-stereotipuri/>.

Hersey, P. and K., Blanchard.

1998

"Management of organizational behavior" in "Management of organizational behavior: Utilizing human resources" (fifth Ed.), Englewood Cliffs, NJ: Prentice Hall, 169–201.

Loden, M.

1985

Feminine Leadership or How to Succeed in Business Without Being One of the Boys, New York, Crown Publisher.

Mckinsey & company.

2021

"Women in the Workplace 2021"; <https://www.mckinsey.com/featured-insights/diversity-and-inclusion/women-in-the-workplace>.

Pew Research Center.

2008

Men or Women: Who's the Better Leader? A Paradox in Public Attitudes, Report / august 25, 2008.

Pigeyre, F., Vernazobres, P.

2013

Le « management au féminin » : Entre stéréotypes et ambiguïtés, in *Management international / International Management / Gestión Internacional*, Volume 17, 4: 14–256; <https://www.erudit.org/fr/revues/mi/2013-v17-n4-mi01016/1020677ar/>.

Stanculescu, E.

2009

"Stereotipurile de gen din perspectiva cogniției sociale" / "Gender Stereotypes from the Perspective of Social Cognition" in *Revista de Psihologie*, t. 55, 3 – 4, 213–226; https://www.academia.edu/808113/STEREOTIPURILE_DE_GEN_DIN_PERSPECTIVA_COGNITIEI_SOCIALE.

Verawati, D. and M.B., Hartono.

2020

"Effective Leadership: From The Perspective of Trait Theory and Behavior Theory" in *Jurnal REKOMEN (Riset Ekonomi Manajemen)*, Vol. 4, 1: 13–23.